

$3n + 1$ Analysis

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Abstract

The present article analyzes the Collatz conjecture in two fields: loops and divergence. First, the problem of whether there are more loops than the well-known $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$ cycle is addressed. Through an analysis of the loop formula, it is demonstrated that there are no additional loops. Secondly, the problem of divergence sequences that tend to infinity is examined by applying the inverse rules of the Collatz conjecture. The analysis indicates that no such divergence is possible. Consequently, by ruling out both alternative cycles and divergent paths, this work provides evidence that the Collatz conjecture is true for all positive integers.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Statement

The Collatz conjecture, also known as the $3n + 1$ conjecture, was formulated in 1937 by Lothar Collatz and states that for every positive integer, the successive application of the following rules always ends in 1. The rules are:

- If it is even: $\frac{n}{2}$.
- If it is odd: $3n + 1$.

Let's take the number 3 as an example; this number follows the following sequence, $3 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$

1.2 Collatz Equation

Every sequence in the Collatz Conjecture can be expressed by the following algebraic expression:

$$\frac{3^m \cdot n + y}{2^d} = 1$$

Where:

- n is any positive integer.
- m represents the number of times the rule $3n + 1$ is applied.
- d represents the number of times the rule $\frac{n}{2}$ is applied.
- y is the sum of terms of the form $2^a \cdot 3^b$.

If we express the sequence that follows 3 arithmetically, we get:

$$\frac{3 \cdot \left(\frac{3 \cdot 3 + 1}{2}\right) + 1}{2^4} = 1$$

If we simplify the expression, we obtain the following:

$$\frac{3^2 \cdot 3 + 5}{2^5} = 1$$

Whatever number is used, any successive application of the rules of the conjecture will always result in the same structure.

Each time the rule $\frac{n}{2}$ is applied, the denominator is multiplied by 2; therefore, the denominator is a power of 2.

Each time the rule $3n + 1$ is applied, two effects occur in the numerator. On one hand, n is multiplied by 3, and therefore the multiplicand of n is always a power of 3. On the other hand, $+1$ is added to the equation, in order to have a common denominator $1 \cdot 2^a$ is multiplied, and then, if the rule $3n + 1$ is applied, it is also multiplied by 3, resulting in a term of the form $2^a + 3^b$, with y being the sum of all these terms.

2 Loops

2.1 Composition and Nature of a Loop

If a loop existed in the sequence, the set of numbers that compose it would necessarily be finite; otherwise, it could not be classified as a loop since it would never 'start again'.

Each number in that finite set of numbers can generate itself through the rules of the conjecture. Interestingly, each of these numbers shares the variables d and m ; which means that the number of times the rule $3n + 1$ and the rule $\frac{n}{2}$ are applied is the same for all of them; only the order in which they are applied changes.

As an analogy to the above, consider a bus route with several stops. No matter which stop it starts from, the number of times the bus turns right and left until it returns to the same place will always be the same at every stop; only the order changes. These differences in order will alter the value of the variable y .

2.2 Equation of a Loop

Based on the equation described above, the equation of a loop would be the following:

$$\frac{3^m \cdot n + y}{2^d} = n$$

In other words, any n that, after applying the rules of the conjecture, results in n again.

From the previous equation, we can solve for y so that:

$$y = n(2^d - 3^m)$$

From now on, $i = (2^d - 3^m)$, so $y = ni$.

We can draw two conclusions from the variables y and i :

- The variable i is odd, since it is the difference between an even and an odd number.
- There is a parity relation between n and y since, if i is odd, the product of ni will be odd if n is odd, or even if n is even.

If we substitute $y = ni$ into the loop equation, we get:

$$\frac{3^m \cdot n + ni}{2^d} = n \Rightarrow 3^m \cdot n + ni = 2^d \cdot n$$

$$3^m + i = 2^d$$

This gives us a simplified version of the equation that is also independent of n .

2.3 Deviation of +1

To measure how +1 affects the rule $3n + 1$, we will analyze two sequences. One will apply the rules $3n + 1$ and $\frac{n}{2}$, the other simply $3n$ and $\frac{n}{2}$. Starting with the number 9, we get:

$3n + 1$	28	14	7	22	11	34	17
$3n$	27	13.5	6.75	20.25	10.125	30.375	15.1875
Deviation	1	0.5	0.25	1.75	0.875	3.625	1.8125

The differences in the sequences begin the first time the $3n + 1$ rule is applied. If we had started with the number 18, both sequences would have applied the rule $\frac{n}{2}$ and the results would be exactly the same.

Once the rule $3n + 1$ is applied, the sequences deviate by one unit. From then on, the deviation will be divided by 2 when the rule $\frac{n}{2}$ is applied, and multiplied by 3 and then 1 added to it when the rule $3n + 1$ is applied.

If we are in a loop and apply the rules $3n$ and $\frac{n}{2}$, the result differs from the original in the proportion expressed above. If we were to sum the deviations, we would have the same result as applying the ordinary rules of the conjecture, so that:

$$3^m + h - 2^d = 3^m + i - 2^d \implies d = i$$

Where h is the aforementioned deviation. In this case we are using the simplified loop equation.

If the rule $3n + 1$ is applied only once, the variable h can be calculated using the following expression:

$$\frac{1}{2^{d-k}} = h$$

Where k is the number of divisions by 2 that have taken place before the rule $3n + 1$ is applied, because until then the sequences are exactly the same.

If the rule $3n + 1$ is applied a second time, then the deviation at the time the rule is applied will be:

$$3\left(\frac{1}{2^{d-k}}\right) + 1 = h$$

If it is applied a third time:

$$3\left(\frac{3}{2^{d-k}} + \frac{1}{2^{d-k-z}}\right) + 1 = h$$

Where z represents the number of divisions by 2 that have taken place since the last time the rule $3n + 1$ was applied.

Finally, if it is applied a fourth time:

$$3\left(\frac{3^2}{2^{d-k}} + \frac{3}{2^{d-k-z}} + \frac{1}{2^{d-k-z_1}}\right) + 1 = h$$

The structure of the above would be the following:

$$\frac{3^{m-1} + \sum_{b=1}^{m-2} 2^a \cdot 3^b}{2^{d-k}} + 1 = h$$

2.4 Relationship between the variables i , 2^d , and 3^m .

From the equation $y = ni$, it follows that:

- $\frac{y}{n} = i$
- $\frac{n}{y} = \frac{1}{i}$
- $1 = \frac{ni}{y}$

From this last equation, it follows that:

$$1 = \frac{n(2^d - 3^m)}{y} \Rightarrow 1 = \frac{2^d \cdot n}{y} - \frac{3^m \cdot n}{y}$$

$$2^d \cdot \frac{n}{y} = 3^m \cdot \frac{n}{y} + 1$$

If we now substitute $\frac{n}{y} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2^d-3^m}$:

$$2^d \cdot \frac{1}{2^d - 3^m} = 3^m \cdot \frac{1}{2^d - 3^m} + 1 \Rightarrow$$

$$\frac{2^d}{2^d - 3^m} - \frac{3^m}{2^d - 3^m} = 1$$

This last expression leads us to conclude that:

- $2^d > i$
- $3^m < i$

Or alternatively:

- $2^d > i$
- $3^m > i$

2.5 Case where $3^m < i$

This section assumes that we are dealing with the case where $3^m < i$.

It was previously concluded that for a loop to exist, the following equality must be true: $h = i$. The only case in which the equality holds is when $d = 2$ and $m = 1$.

To demonstrate the above, the following table shows the exponents of 3 from 1 to 10, the first exponent of 2 that fulfills the rule $3^m < i$, and finally the difference of powers i .

m	d	i
1	2	1
2	5	23
3	6	37
4	8	175
5	9	269
6	11	1319
7	13	6005
8	14	9283
9	16	45853
10	17	72023

From this table It can already be inferred that the growth of i is much greater than the growth of h . The highest value that can be obtained with h , ignoring the remaining divisions by 2, would be to start with 1 and alternate divisions and multiplications, always ending with a multiplication; these operations would be performed a total of m times. I reiterate that this maximum value is incorrect because it does not take into account the remaining divisions by 2; however, it is useful for seeing the growth between the two variables. The following table shows the aforementioned growth:

i	h
1	1
23	2.5
37	4.75
175	8.125
269	13.1875
1319	20.78125
6005	32.171875
9283	49.2578125
45853	78.88691875
72023	113.3300781

Just to clarify the calculations, h_1 differs from the next h_2 as follows:

$$3\left(\frac{h_1}{2}\right) + 1 = h_2$$

From the equation above, we can determine that the growth of h is represented by the following expression:

$$h_{j+1} = 1.5h_j + 1$$

It follows that the growth of h is exponential with base 1.5.

Conversely, the growth of i is, fundamentally, exponential. Given the rule $i > 3^m$, the next i must be greater than the next power of 3. Certainly, i will fluctuate sometimes well above the next power of 3 and sometimes closer, but never below. Thus, we can conclude that there is a hidden exponential growth in the variable i .

If the growth of h is $O(1.5^m)$, and that of i is $O(3^m)$, then $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} |i(m) - h(m)| = \infty$.

Thus we can conclude that, for the case of $3^m > i$, the variables h and i are only equal in the case of $d = 2$ and $m = 1$.

2.6 Case where $3^m > i$

The previous section is insufficient for the case where $3^m > i$ because in this case we cannot guarantee that the growth of i is $O(3^m)$. However, there is another argument that allows us to show that $i = h$ only in the case of $d = 2$ and $m = 1$; this argument is applicable in the case of $3^m > i$ or $3^m < i$. If we know that i is an integer, then h must also be an integer; however, h was calculated based on the following equation:

$$\frac{3^{m-1} + \sum_{b=1}^{m-2} 2^a \cdot 3^b}{2^{d-k}} + 1 = h$$

The numerator of this equation will always be an odd number because it involves the sum of an odd number plus a summation that results in an even number. Since the denominator is a power of 2, the result can never be an integer. This equation was certainly developed under the assumption that the last step applied is the rule $3n + 1$; however, if a number is a decimal, no matter how many times it is divided by 2 afterward, it will remain a decimal.

The only scenario in which h can be an integer is when the rule $3n + 1$ is applied only once and, furthermore, $k = d$. This is the case with the number 4, which is why it forms the loop $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$.

3 Divergence

In this section, we will rule out the possibility of any sequence that, instead of ending at 1, tends to infinity.

3.1 Reverse Collatz Conjecture

To prove the non-existence of divergence, we will apply the rules of the conjecture in reverse. Instead of starting from any number and reaching number 1, we will start from 1 to infinity.

The rules of the reverse Collatz conjecture differ somewhat more than expected from the original rules. This is because, while an odd number can only be obtained using the rule $\frac{n}{2}$, an even number can be obtained using the rules $\frac{n}{2}$ or $3n + 1$. For this reason, in some cases, it will be necessary to apply both rules to an even number creating ramifications as will be shown below.

The reversed Collatz rules are:

- If n is odd: $2n$.

- If n is even: $2n$ and/or $\frac{n-1}{3}$

A graphical example of the application of these rules would be the following:

The numbers 16 and 10 are examples of cases where both rules can be applied simultaneously.

By applying these rules, we are tracing the path that an ordinary Collatz sequence would trace, but in reverse, forming a branching tree. Thus, if any number appears in that tree, it means that it has a path to 1 and therefore satisfies the Collatz conjecture.

3.2 Contagion Effect.

One of the conclusions that can be drawn from the inverse application of the conjecture is what I call the 'contagion effect'. If a number 'p' satisfies the conjecture, the next number generated by applying the inverse rules also satisfies the conjecture; it has been 'infected' by its predecessor.

This can be demonstrated with the following argument. If, in reverse, p generates p_1 , then in ordinary terms, p_1 generates p , and since p_1 leads to a number that does end in 1, then p_1 also ends in 1 and, therefore, satisfies the conjecture. This same argument can be made with respect to p_2, p_3, p_4 , etc.

3.3 The reverse Collatz conjecture tends to infinity.

Another conclusion that can be drawn from the inverse application of the conjecture's rules is that there are infinitely many numbers that satisfy the ordinary Collatz conjecture.

This occurs because for every number, even or odd, the rule $2n$ will always apply, generating an infinite sequence of multiplications by 2. This can be seen in the previous graphic example with the powers of 2, but also with the trail generated by other numbers such as 3 or 5.

3.4 Brief reference to the nodes.

Let's call an input node any number that, when applying the rules of the conjecture in either direction, generates 'p'. Let's call an output node the

number that generates 'p' when the rules of the conjecture are applied in either direction.

On the other hand, the 'set of input nodes' consists of all the numbers necessary to reach 'p', and the 'set of output nodes' would be all the numbers generated by 'p' and its successors.

The following graph of the conjecture in reverse direction serves as an example:

Given $p = 10$, the input node is 5 and the output nodes are 3 and 10.

Every number has only one input node. In the ordinary sense, it also has only one output node. In reverse sense, there are numbers that have two output nodes.

3.5 Disjoint component.

Proving that the Collatz tree is infinite is not enough; it is also necessary to prove that it is exhaustive, that is, that it includes all positive integers.

To do this, let's consider what an 'disjoint component' would be: a number that does not appear in the tree generated when the rules of the conjecture are applied in reverse.

This disjoint component must be a positive integer. We can also apply the rules of the conjecture to this number in either direction: $3n+1$, $\frac{n}{2}$, $2n$, and/or $\frac{n-1}{3}$. The numbers thus generated (the nodes of the disjoint component) must also be disjoint components; if at any point they generated a number that is in the inverse conjecture tree, they would cease to be disjoint because a path to the number 1 would have been discovered for all of them due to the aforementioned contagion effect. Thus, an disjoint component generates a set of disjoint input and output nodes.

If we analyze the set of output nodes of the disjoint component in reverse, they form an infinite set for the same reason mentioned in point 3.3. For an disjoint component to exist, this infinite set of output nodes must never intersect the also infinite set of numbers that satisfy the conjecture. In other words, we would be dealing with a reverse Collatz conjecture within a reverse Collatz conjecture, which, so to speak, never 'touch' each other.

While it could be argued that such an assumption is theoretically possible because the contrary has not been proven, the real reason why these disjoint

components cannot exist lies in the set of input nodes.

Unlike the set of output nodes, the set of input nodes cannot extend to infinity because that would imply the disjoint component has no logical origin.

The only way for this disjoint component to persist would be if its input nodes were to eventually intersect its output nodes, forming a loop.

However, as explained in point 2, there are no loops other than the one mentioned $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2$, so this hypothesis must also be discarded.

In conclusion, the Collatz conjecture in reverse is infinite and exhaustive because no disjoint component can exist.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the Collatz conjecture is true because:

- There are no more loops than $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2$.
- An disjoint component can not exist. Therefore every number satisfies the conjecture and there can be no divergence.

Therefore, the Collatz conjecture is proven to be true.